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ETHICS AND GOOD FAITH IN CONTRACTS IN THE DIGITAL AGE AND PERSONAL DATA PROTECTION

Rezumat. Articolul analizează aspecte legate de modul în care digitalizarea fără precedent și dezvoltarea sistemelor de inteligență artificială și utilizarea acestora la încheierea contractelor își pun amprenta principiul bunei-credințe în contracte, consacrat în dreptul contractelor, astfel încât să fie menținut echilibrul contractual. În articol sunt analizate cerințele pentru contracte impuse de utilizarea etică a inteligenței artificiale, pentru a asigura o folosire transparentă și responsabilă a inteligenței artificiale la negocierea, la încheierea și la executarea contractelor. În articol, buna-credință în contracte este analizată în strânsă legătură cu protecția datelor cu caracter personal, conform Regulamentului General privind Protecția Datelor (GDPR). În articol sunt subliniate provocările legate de necesitatea protejării

dreptului la viață privată și a dreptului la protecția datelor cu caracter personal, ca manifestare a bunei-credințe în contractele încheiate în era digitală.

Cuvinte cheie: contract, inteligență artificială (AI), date personale, GDPR, bună credință, etică, digitalizare

Abstract. The article analyzes aspects related to how unprecedented digitalization and the development of artificial intelligence systems and their use in concluding contracts affect the principle of good faith in contracts, regulated in contract law, so as to maintain contractual balance. The article analyzes the requirements for contracts determined by the ethical use of artificial intelligence, in order to ensure a transparent and responsible use of artificial intelligence in the negotiation, conclusion and execution of contracts. In the article, good faith in contracts is analyzed in close connection with the protection of personal data, according to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). The article highlights the challenges related to the need to protect the right to privacy and the right to the protection of personal data, as a manifestation of good faith in contracts concluded in the digital age.

Keywords: contract, artificial intelligence (AI), personal data, GDPR, good faith, ethics, digitalization

Considerations on the impact of artificial intelligence on contracts and personal data protection, with advantages and risks. The Artificial Intelligence Act (AI Act)¹ is the first law on artificial intelligence in the world and represents a huge step towards a regulation dedicated to the use of artificial intelligence systems and the development of artificial intelligence in a safe framework, which encourages the development of technology and innovation while respecting fundamental rights. At the European Union (EU) level, artificial intelligence policy focuses on regulations and strategies that encourage the development of artificial intelligence systems because there are many benefits brought by new technologies, but in a responsible way, respecting limits and obligations by providers and developers of artificial intelligence systems, which limit the risks of these new technologies.

The use of artificial intelligence has a major impact on the business environment and especially on contracts, with the general emphasis on the advantages brought to the field of contracts, advantages that exist throughout the contractual process, regardless of whether it is the contract negotiation stage or the contract conclusion and execution stage, through the contribution made to efficiency, accelerated process development, cost reduction, rapid analysis of a large volume of data, automation of processes or reduction of the risk of human error.

Beyond the advantages, the use of artificial intelligence in contracts is not without risks, which must be analyzed from both a legal and ethical perspective. The European Union emphasizes the development of safe, legal, trustworthy artificial

¹ Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 June 2024 laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence (Artificial Intelligence Act), OJ L, 2024/1689, 12.7.2024, [https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/RO/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32024R1689\(01.05.2026\)](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/RO/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32024R1689(01.05.2026));

intelligence that benefits people and takes into account the interests of people, the well-being of people and fundamental rights.

The traditional contract appears reconfigured in a vision that must take into account, beyond the rights and obligations of the parties, new limits, which determine new requirements for contracts: first, conditions established by the Regulation on artificial intelligence, and then, additional requirements established by the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)¹, which sets the standard for the protection of personal data.

Ethical implications of using artificial intelligence in contracts, good faith, responsibility and personal data protection. According to Article 14 of the New Romanian Civil Code², any natural or legal person must exercise their rights and perform their obligations in good faith, in accordance with public order and good morals; there is a presumption of good faith, until proven bad faith.

In contracts, good faith means loyalty and honesty in the relations between the contracting parties³. Article 1170 of the Romanian Civil Code regulates the principle of good faith in contracts: “The parties must act in good faith both when negotiating and concluding the contract, and throughout its execution. They cannot remove or limit this obligation.” Furthermore, Art. 1183 of the Civil Code places a distinct emphasis on good faith at the stage of contractual negotiations, since “the party that engages in a negotiation is required to respect the requirements of good faith”, without the parties being able to limit or exclude this obligation; The Civil Code considers contrary to the requirements of good faith the conduct of the party that initiates or continues negotiations without the intention of concluding the contract, and the party that initiates, continues or breaks the negotiations contrary to good faith is liable for the damage caused to the other party.

The principle of good faith must be respected at all stages of the contract, when negotiating, concluding and executing contracts, and the fact that artificial intelligence can be used at all these contractual stages means that compliance with good faith in contracts must be correlated with measures that ensure the safe use of artificial intelligence in contracts, which ensure the trust of the parties in the online environment, in order to guarantee contractual balance.

The Regulation on artificial intelligence promotes ethical, safe and reliable artificial intelligence. It is necessary to have reliable artificial intelligence, which is legal in order to ensure respect for fundamental rights and freedoms, which is ethical, meaning that it ensures respect for ethical values, and which is robust⁴, meaning that

¹ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation), <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/RO/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A02016R0679-20160504> (03.05.2026);

² Romanian Civil Code, Law no. 287/2009. Official Gazette no. 505/2011;

³ Dimitrie Gherasim, *Buna credință în raporturile juridice civile*, Bucharest, Romanian Academy Publishing House, 1981;

⁴ AI HLEG-High-level expert group on artificial intelligence of The European Commission, *Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI*, Brussels, 8.04.2019, p. 5, https://www.europarl.europa.eu/meetdocs/2014_2019/plmrep/COMMITTEES/JURI/DV/2019/11-06/Ethics-guidelines-AI_RO.pdf (03.05.2026);

it functions in the interest of humanity and for the good of people, without intentional harm and without discrimination.

Thus, the principle of good faith in contracts is complemented by the requirements of the Regulation on artificial intelligence regarding legal, ethical and robust artificial intelligence, which outline the idea of honesty and loyalty between contracting parties, in the digital age.

The Regulation on artificial intelligence, which entered into force on 1.08.2024, has a risk-based approach and specific requirements depending on the risks existing for AI systems¹. Ethics regarding the use of artificial intelligence in contracts means, beyond the requirements imposed by the Civil Code, the link between responsibility, good faith, the requirements for safe, ethical and reliable artificial intelligence.

Artificial intelligence experts have highlighted ethical principles² that must be respected by artificial intelligence systems, which are closely linked to the respect of fundamental rights and which have a major impact on contracts in which artificial intelligence is used: respect for human autonomy, prevention of harm, fairness and explainability; emphasis is placed on supporting vulnerable groups and on adopting appropriate and proportionate measures if AI systems pose risks to individuals or society. For example, the use of AI systems that use manipulative or deceptive techniques, with the aim of distorting a person's behavior in order to induce them to make a certain decision, is prohibited.

The use of artificial intelligence in contracts means the use of large volumes of data and can lead to violations of the right to privacy and the right to the protection of personal data; there are risks related to excessive data collection, which exceed the requirement for data necessary for the conclusion or execution of a contract, there is a risk of automatically generated clauses, without human supervision, or decisions taken by artificial intelligence systems that are not explained to the parties in a transparent manner. Thus, where personal data are processed in contracts, the principles of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) must be respected, in order to ensure respect for the rights of the parties and to maintain contractual balance.

The protection of personal data of natural persons is a fundamental right, according to Article 8(1) of the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union and according to Article 16(1) of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU), regulating the right of every person to the protection of personal data concerning him or her.

In addition to the requirements regulated by the Romanian Civil Code regarding the rights and obligations of the parties to contracts, the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) requires compliance with transparency and accountability requirements. Data processing is only lawful if there is a legal basis for processing (from Article 6 GDPR): the consent of the data subject; contractual

¹ European Council, Council of the European Union, Explainers: Artificial intelligence act, <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/ro/policies/artificial-intelligence-act/> (3.05.2026);

² AI HLEG, *Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI*, *op. cit.*, p. 2;

basis, i.e. the conclusion or performance of a contract, in the sense that processing is lawful if it is necessary for the performance of a contract to which the data subject is party or to take steps at the request of the data subject prior to entering into a contract; legal obligation; performance of a task carried out in the public interest; vital interest of the person; legitimate interest.

The European Data Strategy¹ aims to create a single market for data and a common European data space and emphasizes the idea of European citizens having control over their own data.

A contractual balance is required between the contracting parties, but there also needs to be a balance of interests between the data controller (who processes the individual's data) and the interest and rights of the data subject (the individual whose data is processed by the controller). The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) aims to protect the rights of the data subject, which adds to the requirements imposed on the contracting parties.

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¹ Communication from The Commission to The European Parliament, The Council, The European Economic And Social Committee And The Committee Of The Regions, *A European strategy for data*, COM/2020/66, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/RO/ALL/?uri=CELEX:52020DC0066> (05.05.2026); The Data Governance Act (which aims to facilitate the exchange of personal and non-personal data) and the Data Regulation (Data Act) also contribute to these objectives. Regulation (EU) 2022/868 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2022 on European data governance and amending Regulation (EU) 2018/1724 (Data Governance Act), OJ L 152, 3.6.2022, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32022R0868> (02.05.2026); Regulation (EU) 2023/2854 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 December 2023 on harmonised rules on fair access to and use of data and amending Regulation (EU) 2017/2394 and Directive (EU) 2020/1828 (Data Act), OJ JO L, 2023/2854, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2023/2854> (2.05.2026);

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КРИЗОВІ ЯВИЩА В СИСТЕМІ ОХОРОНИ ЗДОРОВ'Я І СТРАТЕГІЇ ЇХ ПОДОЛАННЯ

У сучасних умовах глобальних викликів, зокрема пандемій, воєнних дій та соціально-економічної нестабільності, ефективне функціонування системи охорони здоров'я набуває критичного значення. Кризові явища у системі охорони здоров'я проявляються у зростанні навантаження на медичну інфраструктуру, обмеженості ресурсного забезпечення, кадровому дефіциті та підвищенні рівня захворюваності населення. Це обумовлює необхідність розробки та впровадження дієвих стратегій подолання кризових явищ і підвищення стійкості галузі. Традиційні методи реагування часто є неефективними. Потрібні довгострокові стратегії, спрямовані не лише на